

THE IMPORTANCE OF PUBLIC ORGANIZATIONS IN EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM

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Abstract: any state sees its perspective in the image of a healthy and harmonious generation. The process of large-scale reforms carried out in our country, the realization of such noble goals as building a strong civil society and a democratic state governed by the rule of law, is unthinkable without the participation of young people. Educating young people at the level of the requirements of the time, patriotism, strengthening the sense of belonging to this dear Motherland, strengthening health, education and upbringing of a generation with high strength, knowledge and potential, a broad worldview and independent thinking are the priorities of our state's policy.

Keywords: fatherland, patriotism, education, spirituality, ideology, effectiveness of education, sense of Homeland.

ЁШЛАРНИ ВАТАНПАРВАРЛИК РУҲИДА ТАРБИЯЛАШДА ЖАМОАТ ТАШКИЛОТЛАРИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ

Аннотация: Ҳар қандай давлат ўз истиқболини соғлом ва баркамол авлод тимсолида кўради. Мамлакатимизда амалга оширилаётган кенг кўламли ислохотлар жараёнини, кучли фуқаролик жамияти ва ҳуқуқий демократик давлат қуришдек эзгу мақсадлар рўёбини ёшлар иштирокисиз тасаввур этиб бўлмайди. Ёшларни замон талаблари даражасида таълим–тарбия олиши, ватанпарвар бўлиши, шу азиз Ватанга дахлдорлик ҳиссини кучайтириши, саломатлигини мустаҳкамлаши, ўз кучи, билим ва салоҳиятини юқори, дунёқараши кенг, мустақил фикрлайдиган авлодни вояга етказиш ва тарбиялаш давлатимиз сиёсатининг устувор йўналишларидандир.

Калит сўзлар: ватан, ватанпарварлик, таълим-тарбия, маънавият, мафкура, таълим самарадорлиги, ватан туйғуси.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ В ПАТРИОТИЧЕСКОМ ВОСПИТАНИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

Аннотация: любое государство видит свою перспективу в образе здорового и гармоничного поколения. Процесс масштабных реформ, осуществляемых в нашей стране, реализация таких благородных целей, как построение сильного гражданского общества и правового демократического государства, немыслим без участия молодежи. Воспитание молодежи на уровне требований времени, патриотизм, укрепление чувства сопричастности к этой дорогой Родине, укрепление здоровья, воспитание и формирование поколения, обладающего высокими силами, знаниями и потенциалом, широким мировоззрением и независимым мышлением, являются приоритетными направлениями политики нашего государства.

Ключевые слова: отечество, патриотизм, воспитание, духовность, идеология, эффективность воспитания, чувство Родины.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan is demographically considered a country of youth. Indeed, the problems associated with youth are extremely relevant today for the prospects of any country. The spiritual maturity of youth is a broad enough concept, and on the basis of this understanding, it becomes important to educate a healthy generation with a healthy worldview. After all, the main goal of education is to lead a conscious life in society, to create a highly culturally intelligent and comfortable environment.

The process of personality maturation is complex and proceeds under the influence of a person's program in his hereditary units, personal ambitions and under the influence of the external natural and social environment, as well as purposeful educational processes. [1,78] Youth policy developed in connection with radical changes and the processes of restructuring society. The state policy towards youth in the first years of independence was aimed at protecting the socially needy strata, building a democratic and civil society, introducing market relations into the economy, increasing legal literacy of the population, ensuring and empowering young people to education, forming a sense of patriotism among young people, at the next stage, young people were considered as a force forming the personnel the country's reserve in the modernization of society.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In most developed countries, state programs for patriotic education of citizens, Concepts for improving the effectiveness of military-patriotic education have been adopted, numerous public veteran and public organizations have been created that are engaged in patriotic education of young people and provide financial support from the state. At the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a new stage of reforms in the field of the country's state policy in the military sphere has begun, increasing the defense capability of our Armed Forces. The Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, talking with military personnel and listening to reports of officials, also pointed out serious, systemic problems that have accumulated in the industry over many years, noting that "this is a personnel issue, providing troops with modern weapons, social protection of military personnel, issues related to the education of youth and military personnel in the spirit of military patriotism"[2].

Educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is an issue that never loses its relevance and significance for all of us. This topical issue is a continuous process consisting of a complex of interrelated political and legal, socio-economic, ideological and ideological, cultural and educational activities. Today, work on military-patriotic education of young people is carried out in accordance with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, general military charters of the Armed Forces and other legislative acts.

In particular, in the "state program on the implementation of the strategy of actions in the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" in the "year of support for Youth and strengthening public health", on the basis of the "Patriot" organization, the responsibility is assigned to assist young people in teaching professions with high At the same time, it was also said that propaganda work is carried out in improving their military knowledge, skills and abilities.

Military-patriotic education is a component of general education-upbringing. The basis of military-patriotic education is patriotic education. Accordingly, military-patriotic education is based on patriotic education, which is an integral part of all education and upbringing, knowledge,

faith, worldview, which every citizen and growing or Generation Master from the smallest youth periods. The concept of patriotic education means wider than the ratio to the concepts of military-patriotic education and education.

It is clear to all of us that military-patriotic education is a component of general education and is aimed at the formation of readiness and the ability to selflessly defend the motherland in young people. Its spiritual and educational and theoretical basis is the conclusions of modern relevant fields of science on the protection of the Motherland, the historical and modern practical experience of our people about the motherland and its protection, scientific heritage, as well as universal values and modern requirements related to this issue[3, 56].

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The role and importance of upbringing in the spirit of military-patriotic is growing in conditions of increasing confrontation in the current information space, especially the struggle for the consciousness and soul of the younger generation. The fact that the subject of "initial preparation until the call" is reduced from 2 hours to 1 hour gives students a broad and comprehensive explanation of the content of regulatory legal acts, in which weekly hours are quantitatively scarce in the formation of patriotic feelings. These and the above problems should be identified and the directions of preparation of young people in the spirit of patriotism should be improved. In this:

1. To revise the plans for cooperation with the Defense Departments of public educational institutions and to establish control of the deputies of the local council of people's deputies on the implementation of the plan;
2. Re-consideration of the rates of the category of the post of deputy director for youth training in the spirit of patriotism in terms of periodic activity – the head of military training;
3. To include in the annual plan of the Combat Training Department of the military district the organization of field training for students and to load the tasks of providing students with equipment, military uniforms, food for carrying out and bringing;
4. In the military unit attached to the school by agreement of cooperation, it is necessary to expand the scope of the practice of allowing students to shoot electronically at the site of electronic fire once a month.

CONCLUSION

The state is the main institution that provides for the organization of a system of educating young people in the spirit of military-patriotic, monitoring of its results. The state organizes the educational process of the younger generation in the family, preschool education, general secondary education, vocational training and higher educational institutions, during military service, as well as within the framework of citizens' self-government bodies, various state and non-governmental non-profit organizations.

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